

PRACTICAL ASSIMILATION OF DIGITAL TOOLS AND MATERIALS BY TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN MODERN EDUCATION

Saidova Zulfizar Urokovna

Senior teacher, Department of "Foreign Languages",
Tashkent Architecture and Civil Engineering University
Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525677>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st January 2023

Accepted: 10th January 2023

Online: 11th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Digital educational tools, multimedia, computer graphics, sound, video frames, static texts, images, curriculum planning, learning autonomy, higher education

ABSTRACT

The research results represent an overview of modern digital tools in a foreign language, tested in classroom and independent work of students, as well as an analysis of the relationship between the use of multimedia and improving the efficiency of teaching foreign languages. The article examines the educational potential and advantages of using digital technologies in teaching foreign languages in a higher educational institution of a non-linguistic profile. The method-containing result includes recommendations on the methodology for integrating digital technologies into the educational process for organizing classroom work and independent work of students when teaching a foreign language at a university.

A foreign language is an academic subject in which it is supposed to create an artificial language environment for students, which predetermines the variable inclusion of various digital teaching aids in new perspectives of teaching a foreign language.

Digital learning tools are interactive systems that allow you to simultaneously work with animated computer graphics, sound, video frames, static texts and images. The user, the student, is simultaneously influenced through various information channels, where he, the user, is assigned an active role.

Digital class - Among the online resources that help create multimedia lesson plans and deserve mention and implementation in the independent and classroom work of students, we can highlight Google Docs, or Google Docs. It is a free-of-charge application that mimics MS Office online and includes a text editor, spreadsheet editor, a service for creating presentations, and a cloud-based file storage service. Another advantage of the program is that you do not need to download and install it. Its application provides a connection between a teacher and a student in a synchronous and asynchronous mode, allowing you to instantly correct existing shortcomings, misunderstandings or misunderstandings; creation of individual and collective projects autonomously or under the supervision of a teacher; an increase in the volume of tasks solved together with the teacher. [eight]

Digital learning technologies have enormous learning potential. It is necessary to test in a real educational context their ability to stimulate various types of speech activity and the ability to organize a contact and non-contact educational process in a new way.

In all the existing and constantly updated diversity, it is necessary to create and update in real time some typology of digital technologies in teaching a foreign language, to determine the possibilities of their use and to model the methodology for working with them in the context of a change in the methodological paradigm. In improving the material base, software and methodological support, in the acquisition of relevant experience, teachers see the prospect of the successful implementation of the digitalization of education. [1] Below are modern digital tools for teaching a foreign language and some recommendations on how to work with them in order to stimulate the cognitive activity of students. [Cf. 2-3]

Multimedia lesson- an educational lesson using digital technologies, various programs and technical means to effectively influence the student.

Tasks solved with the help of multimedia in foreign language classes include enhancing classroom work; simulating real communication; providing information support; development of cognitive interest and motivation to learn a foreign language. [4]

A multimedia lesson, that is, a lesson using various software systems, including simulators, test programs, graphic editors, multimedia presentations, online editable diagrams, table graphs, workshops with the ability to simulate real processes. As the practice of introducing such tools into the educational process shows, their use effectively affects the student, who develops the ability to learn about the world around him, the skills of using knowledge and skills in a real life context; algorithmic thinking; creative thinking; making optimal decisions in a difficult situation; research skills; the ability to process information. In addition, students have an increase in their adaptive abilities to the modern learning environment,

Electronic textbook and a variety of training simulators can be considered the most accessible for the university student audience from multimedia tools.

The electronic textbook attachments contain vocabulary and grammar training programs, as well as additional practice in listening and writing. Curriculum programs have the ability to significantly change the way learning activities are managed and to carry out targeted individualization of learning, which contributes to improving the quality of learning. Working with programs helps students to better perceive new material thanks to graphic images [5].

In the context of teaching general and business English at a university, it is possible to use the following textbooks with electronic applications on CD and on the Internet:

a) Speakout (A1-B2) (Pearson): ActiveBook - an electronic version of the book for students with additional materials, including the ability to watch videos and listen to audio materials with exercises; the MySpeakoutLab component makes it possible to carry out personalized training and evaluate the results online, including options for instant feedback, an automatic progress diary, additional exercises from the resource bank for effective working out of the material, audio and video files, a testing program that allows you to track the success of the material (lesson, intermediate and final tests).

b) Business Result (A1-B2) (OUP): an interactive workbook on CD is a digital resource for students to independently work on grammar, vocabulary and listening.

c) Market Leader (A1-B2) (Pearson): interactive workbook on CD-ROM with exercises on grammar, vocabulary, listening. The online component MyEnglishLab provides additional practice.

d) MyGrammarLab (A2-B2): the online component includes a Diagnostic Test for each level, video tutorials with explanations of grammar rules; tasks and exercises for each section with automatic checking and error analysis; Progress Tests and Exit Tests after each section; tools for practicing pronunciation, listening and checking your answers to exercises in a printed book; some exercises to prepare for international exams.

Multimedia presentations are the next convenient technology for inclusion in the educational process and require a computer and a projector to use them. Presentations can be carried out both synchronously and asynchronously, i.e. be pre-recorded [6].

The way in which presentations are included in a lesson depends on the content of the lesson and its objectives. So, the following are considered effective purposes of application: the process of illustrating and studying new material; consolidation of a new topic; checking the assimilation of the material.

A resource that is a source of presentations in various fields is the Slide Share platform, where teachers can use a collection of ready-made presentations created and posted by colleagues, which significantly reduces the time spent preparing for the lesson. Students can also create presentations on topics to practice presentation skills. With the help of author's presentations, the teacher has the opportunity to present the material in a sequence that is necessary to achieve the goals and objectives of a particular lesson.

Electronic testing is an automated tool for control and assessment of knowledge by a teacher or a self-control tool that provides, along with oral visual control of the results.

The basic resource should be the resource of the Common European Commission for the Proficiency in Foreign Languages (CEFR), which allows you to determine the level of language proficiency according to the scale used in the framework of the Bologna Convention. Also, this resource provides recommendations for learning a language to achieve a particular level, based on the test results.

The multimedia Internet resource presents information (text, animation, graphics, sound, video) interactively, visually, entertainingly, with instant feedback. [7]

Features of the functioning of Internet materials include: 1) openness and accessibility for everyone, both for students and for teachers; 2) free access and editing of any educational materials; 3) the ability to quickly and easily create new digital objects: video and audio fragments, images and texts; 4) the availability of any materials for people with different levels of knowledge and skills in the field of information technology.

All these materials exist, as a rule, in the original version in a foreign language and, therefore, can be used for foreign language classes to develop skills in working with a foreign language as a professional tool.

Instructional video- a type of Internet resource that allows you to view videos and perform tasks for them, which is used both online and offline. Tasks can be either included in the video itself or in special workbooks. Among the most popular resources are the following:

1) Khan Academy is an Internet resource that provides a variety of videos and materials for them for studying and, mainly, repeating materials on various subjects, preparing for international exams. There is a section "Teachers" on the site, which allows you to add assignments to videos online.

2) TED is an electronic resource, the main content of which is made up of video fragments of speeches on topics widely discussed in society. The resource also exists in a TED Ed edition; which contains not only videos, but also lesson plans, questions for the video, schemes for drawing up lesson plans. The program also allows you to track the progress of students in the study of a specific topic, to which the lesson plan and a specific video were linked. Video lectures in English introduce students to the professional field of their education, adding a subject component created by outstanding scientists of the world to the study of a foreign language.

Digital class - Among the online resources that help create multimedia lesson plans and deserve mention and implementation in the independent and classroom work of students, we can highlight Google Docs, or Google Docs. It is a free-of-charge application that mimics MS Office online and includes a text editor, spreadsheet editor, a service for creating presentations, and a cloud-based file storage service. Another advantage of the program is that you do not need to download and install it. Its application provides a connection between a teacher and a student in a synchronous and asynchronous mode, allowing you to instantly correct existing shortcomings, misunderstandings or misunderstandings; creation of individual and collective projects autonomously or under the supervision of a teacher; an increase in the volume of tasks solved together with the teacher.

As a result of the study, we can conclude: the use of various services mentioned in this work is an effective tool for creating presentations, podcasts, video materials with hyperlinks, has a great impact on the content of the lesson, helps students to perceive the studied material with interest. The use of digital technologies opens up new opportunities for both the teacher and the student.

Today, all over the world, the ways of teaching foreign languages are changing every day due to the sometimes forced technical and methodological changes in the learning process. Practical assimilation of digital tools and materials by teachers and students is both a reality and the prospect of their successful application in modern education.

Presentations, podcasts, various tools that help to contain as much information as possible in different graphic forms make each lesson on various lexical, grammatical, colloquial, professional topics brighter, more diverse and memorable.

References:

1. Donovan J. Widening student participation through technology: Universities can gain from employing digital tools in their teaching and learning strategies // Research Information. - 2017 - No. 93. - 15 p.
2. Genova MM 21st century language classroom with digital tools and resources // Industry 4.0. - 2019. - Vol. 4. - No.
3. - Pp. 142-145.3. Olek-Taszarek W. ICT tools for our schools // Foreign Language Education and its Cross-Curricular Links. - 2017. - S. 67-79.

4. Khilchenko T.V., Dubakov A.V. A multimedia lesson of a foreign language and the organizational and technological features of its design // Bulletin of the Shadrinsky State Pedagogical Institute. - 2013.
5. Ivanova E.O. Electronic textbook - subject information and educational environment for independent work of students // Education and Science. - 2015. - No. 5 (124). - S. 118-128.
6. Volkova E.A. Methodological approaches to the use of interactive tools in the process of teaching students of non-pedagogical specialties // Educational technologies and society. - 2015. - T. 18. - No. 3. - S. 502-510.
7. Bower M. A typology of Web 2.0 learning technologies // Educause. - Feb., 2015. - Vol. 8. - 13 p. 8
8. Saloydinova N. S. Lexical and semantic peculiarities and problems of the translation of architectural and construction terminology from English into Russian and uzbek //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 19-22.
9. Saidova Z.U. Teaching English as a second language (ESL) in a broad context and teaching students professional terminology in the course of English for specific purposes (ESP) //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 10 (57). – С. 45-46.